

THE CONTENT OF USING THE HERITAGE OF CENTRAL ASIAN THINKERS IN FORMING STUDENTS' ECOLOGICAL THINKING THROUGH TEACHING NATURAL SCIENCES IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Annotation. The article discusses the content of the use of the heritage of Central Asian thinkers in the formation of environmental thinking among primary school pupil, its forms, methods and directions, theoretical and practical aspects, the use of the heritage of Central Asian thinkers in instilling environmental knowledge in pupil, updating content, the connection of the system of continuous education with science and production, one of the most important problems of the era of globalization of pupil youth is the features of environmental risk management.

Keywords: elementary school, pupil, ecological thinking, thinker, heritage, globalization, problem, form, method, education-training, learning, theoretical, practical, nature, environmental risk, modern requirements, renewal.

The only way to prevent environmental threats in the world is to protect nature and use natural resources wisely. However, it is difficult to achieve the expected results in this regard without forming ecological thinking in the heart of every student. It is undoubtedly important to inculcate in the minds of students the idea that nature has its own laws and that all phenomena and changes in nature are related to each other.

The impact of the subject on the environment and nature is important in eliminating the general environmental risk. The positive nature of this effect requires the promotion of ecological knowledge among the population, including young people, the formation of ecological thinking in them, and the education of

ecological culture. In order to meet the need that has arisen in this regard, the research conducted in the pedagogical direction differs from scientific research in other directions according to its importance.

"Prevention of environmental problems that harm the environment, population health and gene pool" is defined as an important priority task. Also, in our Republic these days, fundamentally updated regulatory and legal documents and the created material and technical base serve to form the culture of environmental safety among elementary school students.

Primary classes, which play an important role in the formation and strengthening of behavioral qualities in the formation of ecological consciousness and culture in students, have certain opportunities. For this reason, focusing on introducing students to the ecological views of Central Asian thinkers in elementary science classes gives positive results. Forming knowledge based on the ecological heritage of the great thinkers of Central Asia in the minds of primary school students will educate them to have a responsible attitude towards the environment and nature.

Environmental education of elementary school students is a problem of national importance, the solution of which depends on the scientific-pedagogical approach to the problem and the determination of effective ways. For this reason, it is necessary to pay serious attention to ensuring the systematic and continuous imparting of environmental knowledge to students in general education schools.

To make sure that the thinkers of Central Asia and the rich spiritual and educational heritage left by them are studied in the following main directions in various fields of science:

- Philosophical views of Central Asian thinkers - ideas that shed light on material existence, object and subject relations, the basis and social laws of social society, and their impact on personal development;

- legal ideas of thinkers - the state, its types and the history of its formation, the content of socio-legal relations between the state and the citizen, the inquiry

and judicial proceedings organized on the basis of them, the ideas put forward on the issues of individual rights;

- educational and scientific views of thinkers, the formation of the system of scientific knowledge, the justification of the classification of sciences, the role of knowledge in ensuring the perfection of the individual, its role in the education of positive qualities for the individual, the theories that prove that it is the basis of cultural and spiritual development;

- Spiritual and moral views of Central Asian thinkers - spiritual and moral qualities, specific aspects of their possession, the decisive influence of the social environment on the formation of a person's spiritual and moral image, spiritual - opinions confirming that the possession of moral qualities is a criterion that determines human maturity;

- psychological theories of thinkers - about the person, his main subject and object of establishing social relations, his ethno-psychological characteristics, their development on the basis of psychological laws, the content of interpersonal relations, etc. scientific hypotheses;

- the pedagogical views of thinkers - the person, the unity of his physiological, physical and mental maturity, the factors that ensure the formation of an individual as a person, the role of education and upbringing in the maturity of a person, the essence of the educational and educational process, social pedagogical laws, students and teachers The scientific basis of the content of teacher relations, the result of pedagogical influence.

The study of the sources testifies to the long history of ecological knowledge and shows that the spiritual heritage of ancestors in this regard has been a guide for generations for centuries. The ecological views of Central Asian thinkers are of great scientific and practical importance even in today's environment, where the deterioration of the environment has worsened.

For example, Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khorazmi, one of the mature thinkers of the Eastern Renaissance, wrote works on mathematics, geography, and history,

and led the measurement of one degree of the earth's meridian arc. The thinker created more than 20 scientific works, most of them covered the ecological state of the environment and people's attitude towards it. Including the thinker's "Indian Account", "Map of the Earth", "Book of History", "Astronomical Tables", "On the Sundial", "Book on Astrology", "Treatise on Jewish Eras and Holidays" and others. ecological ideas are expressed in the works.

It is suitable for elementary school students to provide information about Muhammad al-Khorazmi's land area accounting problems, ways to solve them, and his views on efficient use of land. Also, it should be mentioned that the names of 2,402 geographical objects, including cities, mountains, seas, islands and rivers, are recorded in the works of Alloma in natural history lessons.

The rich cultural heritage of the great scholar Imam Ismail al-Bukhari, which has a unique place in Islamic culture, has its practical significance even today. In this regard, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov stated the following: "Imam al-Bukhari is the pride of not only the Uzbek people, but also the entire Muslim world. The life of the Blessed One is a literal example of scientific and human courage, indomitable will, and unquenchable faith."

Imam Ismail al-Bukhari's book "Al-jame' as-sahih" is of great importance in the spiritual and moral education of elementary school students. The work fully describes the positive qualities characteristic of a person - such qualities as honesty, purity, truthfulness, the issues of their formation in a person, and the long-held ideas in it encourage a person to be virtuous, to do meritorious deeds, and to have a good name. encourages to leave. Also, along with the issues of moral education, the views on the ecological conditions that take a leading place in the daily activities of a person, that is, the content and conditions of his relationship with nature as a consumer, are included in the content of the work.

In Alloma's work "Al-adab al-mufrat" ("Masterpieces of manners"), issues related to human ecology are also analyzed in detail. For example, in the play, "Son, if one mountain oppresses another mountain, this oppressive mountain will

surely be crushed to pieces. That is, tyranny is such a bad behavior that it is also unforgivable. This is not only for humans and animals, but even if a mass like a mountain (inanimate body) attacks each other, it will surely be avenged"; "If a Muslim plants a tree or a crop, and a person, bird or animal eats its harvest, he will be rewarded with ajru."

In conclusion, it can be noted that in the current situation, in which the problems of ecological danger and its elimination are becoming more and more acute, in the process of providing thorough ecological knowledge to elementary school students, it is necessary to effectively use the ecological heritage of Central Asian thinkers, to develop ecological awareness and ecological thinking in them. is considered one of the important conditions of formation.

BOOKS:

1. Avazov Sh. Maktabda ekologik tarbiya.-Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 1992. - 62 b.
2. At-Termiziy, Abu Iso. Ash shamoil an-nabaviya.- T.: Cho'lpon, 1993. -112 b.
3. Al-Buxoriy, Imom Ismoil. Hadis. Al jome' as-sahih. 4-kitob. - T.: - Qomuslar bosh tahririyati, 1997.- 528 b.
4. Atrof-muhit va biz. Bolalar va ota-onalar uchun ekologiya alifbosi / Talqin. - T.: RTM, 2003. -64 b.
5. Bo'riyev O. Al - Farg'oniy va uning ilmiy meros. - T.: O'zbekiston. - 1998, - 67 b.
6. Bahramov A., Sharipov Sh., Nabiyeva M. Tabiatshunoslik darsligi 4-sinf. T.: "Sharq" nashriyot-matbaa aksiyadorlik kompaniyasibosh tahririyati. 2020. - 120 b.
7. Valiyev Z. O'quvchi shaxsini axloqiy shakllantirishda ekologik tarbiya // Uzluksiz ta'lim tarbiya muammolari. - T.: Nizomiy nomidagi TDPI, 1993.- 27-31 b.

8. Roziqov K.X. Muhit va inson ekologiyasining muammolari.
- T.: O‘zbekiston, 1993. -32 b.
9. Xayrullayev M.M. Buyuk siymolar: Markaziy Osiyodagi mashhur mutafakkir va donishmandlar. -T.: Abdulla Qodiriy nomidagi Xalq merosi nashriyoti, 1996,-120 b.
10. Suyunov D.A. Boshlang‘ich sinf o‘quvchilarida ekologik tafakkurni shakllantirishda O‘rta Osiyo mutafakkirlari merosidan foydalanish texnologiyasi. Berlin, Germany. -P 25.